

DESIGN OF AN ELECTRIC GENERATOR CONSISTING OF A MOVING WATER-DRIVEN PLATE AND A CHAIN DRIVE, GEAR CYLINDRICAL WHEEL ACCELERATOR

Major; Renewable energy resources

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Annotation

In this article, theoretical work is conducted on the operation of an electric generator consisting of a water-driven fan and a chain drive, a toothed cylindrical wheel accelerator.

Key words; spur gear, spur gear, chain drive, double bearings, flow rate, driven pinion, transmission overall efficiency

ENTRANCE

Modern new Uzbekistan has a developed energy system. 50% of the energy systems of the Central Asian countries are located in Uzbekistan, and the government has adopted a strategy to provide the country with electricity until 2030. This strategy sets medium and long-term goals for the country's electricity supply from 2020 to 2030. By 2030, increase electricity production from 5,900 MW to 29,200 MW, reduce natural gas consumption in electricity production from 16.5 billion cubic meters to 12.1 billion cubic meters, and reduce electricity transmission losses by 2.35%, and in distribution - it is planned to reduce by 6.5%.

MAIN PART

We use the kinematic scheme presented above to activate the electrogenerator with the help of running water (Fig. 1). In this scheme, on the base (1), moving bladed wheels (2) are mounted on shaft (3). It moves as a result of water flowing at an average speed of 1.5 m/s. Through the disc clutch (4)

controlled from the shaft (3), the chain drive (5) is transmitted to the drive shaft (7) of the accelerator (6). When necessary, it is possible to disconnect the drive from the accelerator shaft through the disc clutch. The spur gear (8) installed on the drive shaft (7) engages with the drive pinion (9) and drives the generator shaft (12) through the shaft 10 with the help of the permanent coupling (11).

1. The kinematic scheme of the operation consisting of the blades, chain drive and cylindrical gear-wheel accelerator that drives the electrogenerator

1- base part; 2-parts; 3.5- blades and drive sprocket shafts; 4- disc clutch; 6- accelerator housing; 7-leading shestyernya; 8th drive gear; 9th leading gear; 10th drive gear wheel shaft; 11- clutch; 12th electric generator. To perform the calculation of the spoked wheel, we take the diameter of the wheel passing over its spokes to be 1500 mm, and the diameter of the hub on which the spoke is installed to be 250 mm. The main dimensions of Parrak are shown in Figure 2.

2-scheme. This how the wheel looks like

If the water flow speed is assumed to be equal to 1.5 m/s, then we assume that this is approximately the rotational speed of the blade v_n , and then we assume that the force of the water mass affects the blade at a distance of 620 mm from its axis.

Through this we will find out $\omega_n = \frac{v_n}{R_n} = \frac{1,5}{0,62} = 2,42, \frac{rad}{s}$

The number of revolutions of the generator shaft should be $n_g=750 \text{ min}^{-1}$ according to the standard. To achieve this, an accelerator, that is, a multiplier, must be installed

between the crankshaft and the generator shaft, for this we determine the number

of transmissions between the $u = \frac{n_n}{n_r} = \frac{23}{750} = 0,03,$

We can find the rotational speed of the n - by the following formula

$$n_n = \frac{30\omega_n}{\pi} = \frac{30 \cdot 2,42}{3,14} = 23 \text{ min}^{-1},$$

We use the given dimensions of the force acting on the blade to determine the torque of the blade shaft.

The actual length of the blade is 625 mm. Taking into account that the water

does not completely reach the base of the screen, we take the length of the worker working under the influence of water as $a=400\text{mm}$, and multiplying the width by $v=600\text{mm}$, we find the surface S , which affects the water on the screen.

$$S=a \cdot v=400 \cdot 600=240000\text{mm}^2=0,24\text{m}^2,$$

Then we can determine the flow of water acting on the filter using the formula below.

$$F=\gamma \cdot h \cdot \omega \cdot S=1000 \cdot 0,14 \cdot 0,24=34 \text{ кг}=340 \text{ H}$$

Here: $\gamma=1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$ – is the weight of the water in an average volume of 1m^3 ;
 $h\gamma=0.14 \text{ m}$ center of gravity of the water acting on the surface of the wall; Let's determine the power generated by the parallel shaft..

$$N_p = F \cdot \vartheta n=340 \cdot 1,5=510 \text{ Vt}$$

If the speed of water flow increases, the power generated by the steam shaft also increases.

The table shows the change in the power, number of revolutions, angular speed and number of transmissions of the drive shaft with the increase in the speed of the water flow.

The effect of the change in the flow rate on the operation parameters of the electric power generation device

1-jadval

The Velocity of running water (m/s)	1	2	3	4	5
The power of running water, Vt	340	680	1020	1360	1700
The speed of the blades (or propeller), min-1	11	31,5	45	62	77
Angular speed of the	1,61	3,2	4,8	6,6	8

propeller , rad/s					
The number of transmissions of the file system	0,014	0,04	0,6	0,8	0,1

When choosing a generator that produces electricity through a propeller shaft, the useful work coefficient of the transmission from the propeller shaft to the generator shaft

Taking γ_{yu} into account, the power it produces is determined:

$$Ng = N_p \cdot \eta_{yu} = 510 \cdot 0,87 = 444 \text{ Vt}$$

$$\eta_{yu} = \eta_z \cdot \eta_r \cdot \eta_p \cdot 2 = 0,92 \cdot 0,96 \cdot 0,99 \cdot 2 = 0,87$$

Here, $\eta = 0.87$ is the overall efficiency

$\eta_z = 0.92$ is the efficiency of the chain drive

$\eta_r = 0.96$ -the efficiency of the cylindrical gear

$\eta_p = 0.99$ -the efficiency of pair of bearings

If we consider $\eta = 0.87$, generators with a certain capacity of electricity production shown in Table 2.2 are used.2-jadval

The velocity of running water, m/s	1	1,5	2	3	4	5
The power of the electrogenerator, Vt	296	444	592	887	1183	1479

When the water flow rate is 1.5 m/s, an electric generator with a power of 0.444 kW and a number of shaft revolutions $n_d = 750 \text{ min}^{-1}$ is selected.

CONCLUSION

Today, electrical equipment, apparatus and other electrical equipment are widely used in various branches of agriculture, as well as in the domestic service of

farms. In particular, the main part of electricity is generated in synchronous electric machines installed in thermal, hydro and nuclear power stations.

Machines and mechanisms that handle products are driven by various electric motors. A machine that converts electrical energy into mechanical energy is called an electric motor. Currently, about 70% of the electricity produced in our Republic is consumed by electric motors. This figure also applies to agricultural sectors.

Scientific and practical work is being carried out to improve the technical and economic indicators of electric motors, which are the main consumers of energy in our country and the world, and to create noiseless motors in order to provide energy to the growing number and capacity of electricity consumers.

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